

APPLICATION OF PHYTONSTIDES AND IMPROVEMENT OF TECHNOLOGY IN STORAGE OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLES

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ABSTRACT

At the current stage of reforms in the country, the implementation of these measures will meet the demand for food products, ensure its security, expand the geography of exports and ensure the long-term sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing and increase the efficiency of the industry. will improve the living conditions of our people.

It is known that the current natural and climatic conditions in our country allow for the sustainable development of agricultural products, especially fruits and vegetables. The President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan pay great attention to the development of fruit and vegetable growing as a priority in the transition to market relations. Indeed, the fact that a significant part of the country's foreign exchange earnings is formed through the sale of fruits and vegetables in foreign markets also indicates the priority of radical reform and rapid development of the industry.

In particular, a number of decrees and resolutions have been adopted in recent years. These include the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2018 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of fruit and vegetable production in the Republic of Uzbekistan" PF-5388 and October 23, 2019

"On agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan". Decree PF-5853 "On approval of the Strategy for the development of the economy for 2020-2030" and on October 17, 2018 "On additional measures to increase the efficiency of export of fruits and vegetables" PQ-3978, March 14, 2019 "On measures to develop agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetables" PQ-4239

The faster the fruit's metabolism, the faster it breaks down. Decreased metabolism depends on the amount and ratio of oxygen and carbon dioxide in the air. Modern methods of storing fruits at home require 3-5% oxygen and 3-11% carbon dioxide.

When closed containers are used, oxygen is reduced and the amount of carbon dioxide is increased to 3-11%. Chemicals (potassium carbonate, potash, diethanolamine) are used to retain the required amount of carbon dioxide. This

method gives good results when used at low temperatures and pressures.

Apples can be stored in the refrigerator for 50-90 days, and pears for up to 200 days. Moisture can be controlled using silica, chalk, kaolin and activated charcoal.

The essence of the next method of fruit storage is the use of sulfur preparations (combustion gas, in the form of a 6% aqueous solution). In this case, the fruits are soaked in sulfate solutions. Long-term storage can also be achieved by immersion in calcium chloride solutions. A 1% solution sprayed on the tree ensures that the fruit is beautiful and well-preserved.

Fruit warehouses should be equipped with air exchange and ventilation systems. However, warehouses may not have racks or floors. This is because the fruits are stored in special containers mounted on stacks. In spring and summer, ice can be placed in a certain part of the fruit warehouse or in a separate chamber to store the fruit.

The most convenient method is a container made of stone and brick, on which ice is placed. Or such a container can be made of wood. This container should be filled with ice and snow in the winter.

Ice storage - This is when the ice is made in the winter and the fruit can be stored on the side of the ice. It is possible to freeze river or drinking water and to bring natural ice from water bodies.

Ice piles are covered with tree branches or straw from the top and sides in a layer about 5 cm thick, and then 0.5-1 m thick wood chips are placed on top of it. Dry leaves and reeds can also be used instead of sawdust to cover.

Low temperatures reduce the respiration rate of vegetables and weaken the energy processes in plant tissues. Their ripening slows down, and the taste, aroma, vitamins, organic acid content and other useful quality indicators of the product change for the better. At the same time, the resistance of chilled vegetables to pathogens is increased, and their longer storage is achieved. At the same time, the resistance of chilled vegetables to disease-causing agents is increased, and their longer storage is achieved. Storage at cold temperatures prevents the development of fungi, bacteria, yeasts that cause waste, and prolongs the shelf life of vegetables from a few weeks to several months (depending on the species and variety).

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